

The Effect of Type of Payment, Sales Promotion, Quality of Service, Price, and Location on Refilling Gallons of Water with Variables of Customer Satisfaction as Intervening Variables (Case Study on Gallons of Refilled Water "Krisna" in Cipayung Village, Cipayung Sub-District)

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Abstract:- This research aims to analyze the effect of Type of Payment, Sales Promotion, Service Quality, Perceived Price, and Location on Repurchasing Galon Water Refills with Customer Satisfaction Variables as Intervening Variables of Service Quality on Purchasing Decisions and Their Implications on Customer Satisfaction with Customer Research Objects from Galon Water Top up "KRISNA". The research design used is a type of quantitative research method and explanatory research. Data was collected using a questionnaire given to 250 respondents, the sampling technique used was sheets that were given directly and filled in by the customer. The data processing method used is PLS. Researchers take the variables in this study are the type of payment (X1), sales promotion (X2), quality of service (X3), perceived price (X4) and location (X5), customer satisfaction (Y1) and repurchase (Y2).

Based on drinking water data (PDAM), the DKI Jakarta area is experiencing a surge in demand for clean water. However, the PDAM's ability to produce clean water is 20.75 m³ which reaches 907 thousand customers (6 percent of DKI Jakarta's clean water needs) (<https://indonesia.go.id/>). For this reason, there are 94 percent of DKI Jakarta residents who have not access to clean water. This is reinforced by the results of Sri Yusniati's research (2021) which states that around 48 percent of the lower middle class in DKI Jakarta use bottled and refilled water as a practical way of to fulfill drinking water in their household (<https://www.beritasatu.com/nasional/>). However, based on statistical data from DISKOMINFOTIK DKI Jakarta Province in 2020, there are several ways for DKI Jakarta residents to meet their needs for clean water, namely 9.62 percent use piped water (PDAM), 0.2 percent use protected wells, 12.63 use pumps and the rest use refill water (packaging and refill gallons) as shown in Figure 1. below.

I. INTRODUCTION

The condition of the soil in DKI Jakarta is predicted to experience a significant decline in the next few years. According to Research Professor in Geotechnology and Hydrogeology or BRIN Robert Delinom in 2021 said that there are several cities located on the Pantura which are continuously experiencing subsidence or land subsidence, namely Jakarta, Indramayu, Semarang and Surabaya. This subsidence is caused by 4 main factors, namely (1) compaction of rocks that are not solid due to alluvial deposits and hard clay rocks, (2) excessive groundwater withdrawal, (3) loading of buildings that are too heavy, and (4) tectonic activity from the mountain. (<https://metro.tempo.co/>). Besides that, according to the results of the 2020 PTRRB BPPT technical study, the City of Jakarta has experienced subsidence in the last 50 years. So there are a number of things that the people of DKI Jakarta should do, namely not exploiting excessive use of groundwater (<https://mediaindonesia.com/humanities>). The subsidence of the land surface in DKI Jakarta has an impact on changing the behavior of the people of Jakarta in obtaining clean water.

Fig 1. Clean Water Needs in DKI Jakarta in 2020

Source: <https://statistik.jakarta.go.id/infographics/air-clean-di-dki-jakarta-tahun-2020/>

There are 500 mineral water companies that are a source of clean water needs for DKI Jakarta residents as shown in figure 1.2 below. Where the mineral water brand Aqua has a market share of 46.7 percent (Market leader). In addition, the people of DKI Jakarta meet their needs for clean water by using re-packaged water (refill gallons), which costs less than mineral water that already has a name.

Fig 2. Data on sales of bottled drinking water from various brands.

Source: (<https://berbagaiminuman.blogspot.com/2019>)

One area of DKI Jakarta that consumes clean water through refill water is East Jakarta, Cipayung District, Cipayung Village. Based on data from Cipayung District, there are eight outputs with a total number of households of 286,829 units. This means that each household needs at least 286,829 gallons of clean water in one day. So that the refill water industry is very attractive in this region.

II. THEORY REVIEW

A. Type of Payment

According to Aly and Trianasari (2020) the payment system is "a system that manages contracts, operating facilities and technical mechanisms used for the delivery, validation and receipt of payment instructions, as well as fulfillment of payment obligations collected through the exchange of "value" between individuals, banks and other institutions, both domestic and inter-state (cross-border). In daily practice, there are two types of payment systems, namely cash payments and non-cash payments. Payment Cash (cash) is the currency that applies in Indonesia, namely the Rupiah which consists of banknotes and coins. Card-based non-Cash (non-cash) payments have developed with various innovations, ranging from debit / ATM cards, credit cards and various types of electronic money.

Handayani (2015), "explains the payment system, which is a system that includes a set of rules, institutions and mechanisms used to carry out transfers of funds to fulfill an obligation arising from an economic activity. The Payment System is a system related to the transfer of a sum of money from one party to another. The media used to transfer the value of money are very diverse, ranging from the use of simple payment instruments to the use of complex systems involving various institutions and the rules of the game. The authority to regulate and maintain the smooth operation of the payment system in Indonesia is carried out by Bank Indonesia as set forth in the Bank Indonesia Law. According to Tirto in Handayani (2015), "payment is an act of exchanging something (money/goods) with the same intent and purpose which is carried out by two or more people".

B. Sales Promotion.

According to Rosaliana (2018) sales promotion is any short-term incentive given to buyers (customers) or sellers (distributors) with the aim of encouraging the purchase or sale of a product. more quickly but only have a short-term effect or get the maximum benefit.

Promotion (promotion) according to Kusuma and Suryani (2017) is an activity that conveys the benefits of the product and persuades consumers to buy the product. Promotion is a tool used to inform and influence the market about a new product or service for a company through advertising, personal selling, sales promotions, or publicity.

Sales promotion tools according to Kotler and Armstrong (2008) are as follows:

➤ Sample

Samples A sample is an offer to try a new product. Sampling is the most efficient method, but also expensive. Some samples are provided free of charge, but some companies charge a low price to cover the cost of producing the product.

➤ Coupon

Coupons are vouchers that offer buyers a discount when buying a certain product. cash refunds Returns are like coupons except that the price reduction occurs after purchase, not at the time of purchase at the retail store.

➤ Special Prices or Discounts

Special offers are discounts offered to consumers on the official price of a product. High quality Freebies are items that are offered for free or at a reduced price as an incentive to purchase a product. special advertising or promotional products Present to consumers in the form of useful embellishments with the advertiser's name, symbol or message printed on them.

➤ *Support Award*

Support awards are cash rewards or other types of rewards given to regular users of certain company products or services.

➤ *Promotion of the Point of Sale (Point of Purchase)*

Point of sale promotion includes displays or demonstrations at the point of sale.

➤ *Sweepstakes Contests and Games.*

The contest requires consumers to provide input in the form of jingles, conjectures, suggestions to be assessed by the jury who chooses the best input. Sweepstakes. requires consumers to register their names to be drawn. Games bring something to customers.

C. Service Quality

Service quality according to William et al (2016) provided by business managers in running a business is the key to maintaining relationships with customers, in addition to satisfaction and loyalty.

Aningsih (2017) has an opinion, service quality is the level of excellence of the services provided by the organization for consumer or customer satisfaction. Aningsih (2017) argues that service quality indicators consist of responsiveness, empathy, physical evidence, reliability, and assurance.

Kotler and Keller argue in Tjiptono (2019) Customer satisfaction is how a person feels after comparing results with his expectations. According to Kasmir (2017), customer satisfaction is evaluated from the ability of a product to meet expectations and create satisfaction. According to Tjiptono to Yusup and Nurmahdi (2020), service quality includes five dimensions of service quality called SERVQUAL, namely: Reliability, the ability to carry out the promised service convincingly and accurately. Responsiveness, willingness to help customers and provide fast service. Assurance, knowledge and courtesy and their ability to communicate trust and confidence. Empathy, the willingness to give deep and special attention to every consumer. Tangibles (tangible objects), appearance, equipment, staff, and communication materials

D. Perceived Price

According to Sari (2020), price is a value expressed in rupiah to facilitate exchange or transaction activities, and can also be interpreted as the amount that consumers must pay to obtain goods and services, known as price.

Lubis (2018) suggests that price is a very important thing that consumers pay attention to when buying a product or service. If consumers are satisfied with the price offered, they will tend to buy the same product repeatedly. In economic theory it is argued that the price of goods or services in market competition is determined by market supply and demand.

Pricing according to Alma (2013) is a decision regarding prices to be followed within a certain period. Price is closely related to consumer satisfaction. Prices are perceived by consumers through the level of fairness, suitability, affordability, and price competitiveness. Kotler and Armstrong (2012) state that price can be seen from a consumer's point of view, often used as an indicator of value where the price is associated with the benefits felt by the customer due to goods and services. Paul Peter and Jerry Olson (2016) said that price perception is closely related to how information about prices is understood by customers and can provide deep meaning for consumers or potential product buyers.

E. Location

Tjiptono (2015), states that location refers to various marketing activities that seek to expedite and or facilitate the delivery or distribution of goods and services from producers to customers or potential customers.

Sunyoto (2015) a very strategic location where there are many potential buyers or customers, in the sense that this location is easy to reach, easy for customers to see and a location that is traveled a lot and inhabited by target customers who have the potential to buy the products or services being sold or offered.

The definition of location according to Kotler and Armstrong (2018) "locations are various activities of the company to make products produced or sold affordable and available to the target market".

F. Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction according to Sudirman and Efendi (2020) is the response and feelings of consumers for the use of a product or service after comparing product performance to what consumers expect from a product or service used.

According to Tijjang (2020), satisfied customers are customers who receive more value from the company. Satisfying consumers means providing additional or services, services, or systems used. Customer satisfaction is very valuable to maintain the existence of these customers to maintain a business or business venture.

Zurnawati et al (2019) explained the notion of customer satisfaction, in this case it is synonymous with the expectations that customers receive for a product or service. Satisfaction is related to the service provider's attitude towards the customer's emotional reactions and expectations.

G. Repurchase

Repeat purchases are a form of customer loyalty (Cahyani et al., 2021) and satisfaction will increase engagement (Zufrie et al., 2021; Dewi et al., 2021). According to Nurhayati and Wahyu (2012) who said repurchase is the desire and action of customers to repurchase a product, because of the satisfaction received according to the desired product. According to (Lucas & Britt, 2012) there are four factors that can influence customer repurchase intention, namely: attention, interest, desire, conviction.

According to Anoraga (Halim 2014) repurchase intention is the decision-making process carried out by customers after making purchases of the products offered or needed by these customers. Repurchase is behavior after purchasing a product. Products or services consumed by consumers provide satisfaction, so customers tend to repurchase these products or services in the future. Repurchase intention can be achieved by building and managing good relationships with customers continue to provide value and increase maximum customer satisfaction (Varga et al., 2014).

H. Framework of Thought

The following is a schematic framework for this research.

Fig 3. Framework of thinking

Based on Figure 2.1, the hypothesis of this study is:

- The type of payment has a significant effect on customer satisfaction of "KRISNA" refill gallons of water

- Sales Promotion has a significant influence on customer satisfaction of "KRISNA" refill gallon water
- Location has a significant influence on customer satisfaction of "KRISNA" refill gallon water
- Quality of service has a significant influence on customer satisfaction of "KRISNA" refill gallon water
- Price has a significant influence on customer satisfaction of "KRISNA" refill gallon water
- Customer satisfaction has a significant effect on customers repurchasing "KRISNA" refill gallon water
- The type of payment has a significant effect on the repurchase of "KRISNA" refill gallons of water
- Sales Promotion has a significant influence on the repurchase of "KRISNA" refill gallons of water
- Location has a significant influence on the repurchase of "KRISNA" refill gallons of water
- Quality of service has a significant effect on the repurchase of "KRISNA" refill gallons of water
- Price has a significant effect on the repurchase of "KRISNA" refill gallons of water

III. RESEARCH METHODES.

The research method is several scientific steps or procedures in obtaining data for research purposes that have specific goals and uses for their users. In this study, researchers used descriptive methods

This type of research is a type of explanatory research. In research.

This researcher uses the method of causal analysis. Causal analysis is research that aims to determine the effect of one or more independent variables on the dependent variable. The variables to be tested are independent variables including Type of Payment (X1), Sales Promotion (X2), Service Quality (X3), Price (X4) and Location (X5) as well as the dependent variable in this study Customer Satisfaction (Y1) and Repurchase (Y2) refill water.

IV. RESEARCH RESULT

A. Convergent Validity

Table 1 Loading Factor and AVE values

Variabel	Indicator	Outer Loading	Cut Value	AVE	Keterangan
Satisfaction Customer	KP1	0,707	0,70	0,583	Valid
	KP2	0,737	0,70		Valid
	Kp3	0,776	0,70		Valid
	KP4	0,886	0,70		Valid
	KP5	0,841	0,70		Valid
	KP6	0,747	0,70		Valid
	KP7	0,618	0,70		Valid
Repurchase	PU1	0,563	0,70	0,537	Valid
	PU2	0,741	0,70		Valid
	PU3	0,729	0,70		Valid
	PU4	0,789	0,70		Valid
	PU5	0,737	0,70		Valid
	PU6	0,726	0,70		Valid
	PU7	0,744	0,70		Valid
	PU8	0,781	0,70		Valid
	PU9	0,760	0,70		Valid
Payment	JP1	0,787	0,70	0,638	Valid
	JP2	0,835	0,70		Valid
	JP3	0,850	0,70		Valid
	JP4	0,715	0,70		Valid
Sales Promotion	SP1	0,594	0,70	0,664	Valid
	SP2	0,789	0,70		Valid
	SP3	0,902	0,70		Valid
	SP4	0,894	0,70		Valid
	SP5	0,856	0,70		Valid
Service Quality	KN1	0,553	0,70	0,523	Valid
	KN2	0,816	0,70		Valid
	KN3	0,574	0,70		Valid
	KN4	0,596	0,70		Valid
	KN5	0,639	0,70		Valid
	KN6	0,649	0,70		Valid
	KN7	0,807	0,70		Valid
	KN8	0,829	0,70		Valid
	KN9	0,829	0,70		Valid
	KN10	0,846	0,70		Valid
Price Perseption	HR1	0,799	0,70	0,659	Valid
	HR2	0,814	0,70		Valid
	HR3	0,828	0,70		Valid
	HR4	0,829	0,70		Valid
	HR5	0,802	0,70		Valid
	HR6	0,800	0,70		Valid
	HR7	0,809	0,70		Valid
Location	LK1	0,846	0,70	0,642	Valid
	LK2	0,872	0,70		Valid
	LK3	0,888	0,70		Valid
	LK4	0,820	0,70		Valid
	LK5	0,801	0,70		Valid
	LK6	0,774	0,70		Valid
	LK7	0,644	0,70		Valid
	LK8	0,738	0,70		Valid

Source: Results of data processing via SmartPLS, 2022

Based on table 1, the loading factor values for all indicators are greater than 0.7 and the AVE values for all constructs are also greater than 0.5. It can be concluded from the data that all indicators in each construct have met the required convergent validity criteria so that it can be said that all indicators are valid.

B. Discriminant Validity

Table 2. Fornell-Larcker Criterion Test Results

	Price Percept	Payment	Consumer Satisfaction	Service Quality	Location	Repurchase	Sales Promotion
Price Percept	0,812						
Payment	0,555	0,799					
Consumer Satisfaction	0,304	0,387	0,763				
Service Quality	0,330	0,523	0,548	0,723			
Location	0,699	0,524	0,347	0,426	0,801		
Repurchase	0,593	0,482	0,416	0,492	0,571	0,733	
Sales Promotion	0,311	0,430	0,521	0,598	0,429	0,278	0,815

Based on the results of the discriminant validity test in the table above, it shows that there are two constructs that have a square root value of AVE below the correlation value with other latent constructs. In this case it can be concluded that this study has a good construct because the roots of the variables have larger roots than the relationships between other variables. So that the construct variables taken fulfill the Discriminant validity test.

Table 3. MTMT

	Price Perception	Payment	Consumer Satisfaction	Service Quality	Location	Repurchase	Sales Promotion
Price Perception							
Payment	0,601						
Consumer Satisfaction	0,306	0,449					
Service Quality	0,302	0,516	0,560				
Location	0,742	0,545	0,338	0,423			
Repurchase	0,625	0,476	0,429	0,491	0,589		
Sales Promotion	0,337	0,523	0,556	0,667	0,463	0,279	

From table 3 of the MTMT table it can be concluded that the value of each HTMT is < 0.9 , so that each variable construct is considered valid with discriminant validity based on HTMT calculations.

Apart from the HTMT test, there is also the VIF Inner Model Test, with the following explanation:

Table 4 Results of Vif Inner Model

	Price Percept	Payment	Consumer Satisfaction	Service Quality	Location	Repurchase	Sales Promotion
Price Percept			2,177			2,186	
Payment			1,821			1,825	
Consumer Satisfaction						1,584	
Service Quality			1,821			1,991	
Location			2,234			2,234	
Repurchase							
Sales Promotion			1,667			1,787	

From Table 4 it can be concluded that there is no VIF value > 5 so there is no multicollinearity problem. This fact is supported by the absence of a strong correlation between independent variables as shown in the table below:

Table 5. Results of Correlation Between Constructs (Latent Variable Correlations)

	Harga	Jenis Pembayaran	Kepuasan Pelanggan	Kualitas Pelayanan	Lokasi	Pembelian Ulang	Sales Promotion
Price Percept	1,000	0,555	0,304	0,330	0,699	0,593	0,311
Payment	0,555	1,000	0,387	0,523	0,524	0,482	0,430
Consumer Satisfaction	0,304	0,387	1,000	0,548	0,347	0,416	0,521
Service Quality	0,330	0,523	0,548	1,000	0,426	0,492	0,598
Location	0,699	0,524	0,347	0,426	1,000	0,571	0,429
Repurchase	0,593	0,482	0,416	0,492	0,571	1,000	0,278
Sales Promotion	0,311	0,430	0,521	0,598	0,429	0,278	1,000

The table above shows that there is no strong correlation between latent variables, so there is no multicollinearity problem. For example, X1 with X2 is $0.430 < 0.9$. Because it is less than 0.9, the correlation between the two is not strong. So, it can be concluded that in the inner model there is no problem of violating the assumption of multicollinearity.

C. Reliability Test

The construct reliability test can be seen from the Cronbach's Alpha value and the Composite Reliability value of each construct. The value of Cronbach's Alpha and composite reliability and what is recommended is greater than 0.7.

Table 6 Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Keterangan
Consumer Satisfaction	0,881	0,906	Reliabel
Repurchase	0,892	0,912	Reliabel
Payment	0,820	0,875	Reliabel
Sales Promotion	0,871	0,906	Reliabel
Service Quality	0,900	0,914	Reliabel
Price Percept	0,914	0,931	Reliabel
Location	0,920	0,934	Reliabel

Source: Results of data processing via SmartPLS, 2022

From the results of the reliability test in table 6 above, it shows that all constructs have Cronbach's Alpha values > 0.7 and Composite Reliability > 0.7 . This indicates that all constructs have met the required reliability or can be interpreted as a questionnaire used as a tool in this study can be trusted and reliable.

D. Inner Model Analysis

➤ R-Square Value/Coefficient of Determination

Table 7 R-square value

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Consumer Satisfaction	0,369	0,356
Repurchase	0,502	0,489

Source: Results of data processing via SmartPLS, 2022

Table 7 shows that the R-Square values on the Y1 and Y2 dimensions are 0.369 and 0.502. The R Square value of the simultaneous influence of X1, X2, X3, X4 and X5 on Y1 is 0.369 with an adjusted r square value of 0.356. Thus, it can be explained that all exogenous constructs (X1, X2, X3, X4 and X5) simultaneously affect Y by 0.356 or 35.6%. Because Adjusted R Square is more than 33% and less than 67%, the effect of all exogenous constructs X1, X2, X3, X4, X5 on Y1 is moderate.

The R Square value of the simultaneous influence of X1, X2, X2, X3, X4, X5 and Y1 on Y2 is 0.502 with an adjusted r squared value of 0.489. Thus, it can be explained that all exogenous constructs (X1, X2, X3, X4, X5 and Y1) simultaneously affect Y2 by 0.502 or 50.2%. Because Adjusted R Square is more than 33% but less than 67%, the effect of all exogenous constructs X1, X2, X3, X4, X5 and Y1 on Y2 is moderate.

The good fitness of fit assessment is known from the Q-Square value which has the same meaning as the determination coefficient (R-Square) in the regression analysis, where the higher the Q-Square, the model can be said to be better or better.

➤ *Data Fit*

The results of calculating the Q-Square value are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Q-Square 1} &= 1 - (1 - R12) \\ &= 1 - (1 - 0.369) \\ &= 0.369 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Q-Square 2} &= 1 - (1 - R22) \\ &= 1 - (1 - 0.502) \\ &= 0.502 \end{aligned}$$

The results of the Q-Square calculation in this study amounted to 0.369 or 36.9% and 0.502 or 50.2%, thus it can be concluded that the model in this study has relevant predictive value, where the model used can explain the information contained in the research data of 36.9% and 50.2%. Based on the data presented in the table above, the Q square values on the dependent (endogenous) variable are 0.369 and 0.502. By looking at these values, it can be concluded that this research has a good observation value because the Q square value > 0 (zero) is 0.369 and 0.502 (Chin, 1998).

➤ *Path Coefficients*

Table 8 Direct Influence Path Coefficient Value

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values
Price -> Consumer Satisfaction	0,075	0,066	0,082	0,923	0,356
Price-> Repurchase	0,326	0,329	0,083	3,907	0,000
Payment -> Consumer Satisfaction	0,049	0,047	0,083	0,589	0,556
Payment -> Pembelian Ulang	0,057	0,050	0,076	0,753	0,452
Consumer Satisfaction -> Repurchase	0,163	0,160	0,073	2,245	0,025
Service Quality -> Consumer Satisfaction	0,327	0,326	0,075	4,376	0,000
Service Quality -> Repurchase	0,294	0,295	0,084	3,488	0,001
Location -> Consumer Satisfaction	0,011	0,025	0,079	0,139	0,889
Location-> Repurchase	0,219	0,229	0,080	2,722	0,007
Sales Promotion-> Consumer Satisfaction	0,276	0,278	0,067	4,118	0,000
Sales Promotion-> Repurchase	-0,203	-0,209	0,078	2,594	0,010

Based on table 8 above, the path coefficient values that can be seen in the P values and T statistics columns are as follows:

- a. Variable X1 (Type of Payment) on Y1 (Customer Satisfaction) is 0.556 and T statistic is 0.589 which means that there is no significant effect on variable Y1 (Customer Satisfaction) because it has a T statistic value <1.96.
- b. Variable X1 (Type of payment) to Y2 (Repurchase) is 0.452 and the T statistic is 0.753 which means there is no significant effect because the T value <1.96
- c. Variable X2 (Sales Promotion) to Y1 (Customer Satisfaction) is 0.000 and the T statistic is 4.118 which means that there is a significant influence on variable Y1 (Customer Satisfaction) because it has a T statistic > 1.96.
- d. Variable X2 (Sales Promotion) to Y2 (Repurchase) is 0.010 and the T statistic is 2.594 which means that there is a significant influence on the variable Y2 (Repurchase) because the T statistic > 1.96
- e. Variable X3 (Quality of Service) to Y1 (Customer Satisfaction) is 0.000 and the T statistic is 4.376, which means that there is a significant influence on variable Y1 (Customer Satisfaction) because it has a T statistic > 1.96.
- f. Variable X3 (Quality of Service) on Y2 (Repurchase) is 0.001 and the T statistic is 3.488, which means that there is a significant influence on the variable Y2 (Repurchase) because the T statistic > 1.96
- g. Variable X4 (Price) to Y1 (Customer Satisfaction) is 0.356 and the T statistic is 0.923, which means that there is no significant effect on variable Y1 (Customer Satisfaction) because it has a T statistic <1.96.
- h. Variable X4 (Price) to Y2 (Repurchase) is 0.000 and the T statistic is 3.907 which means that there is a significant

influence on the variable Y2 (Repurchase) because the T statistic > 1.96

- Variable X5 (Location) on Y1 (Customer Satisfaction) is 0.889 and the T statistic is 0.139 which means that there is a non-significant effect on the variable Y1 (Customer Satisfaction) because it has a T statistic < 1.96
- j. Variable X5 (Location) to Y2 (Repurchase) is 0.007 and the T statistic is 2.722 which means that there is a significant influence on the variable Y2 (Repurchase) because the T statistic > 1.96
- k. Variable Y1 (Location) to Y2 (Repurchase) is 0.025 and the T statistic is 2.245 which means that there is a significant influence on the variable Y2 (Repurchase) because the T statistic > 1.96

➤ Model Fit

Table 9 SRMR /Model Fit Coefficient Values

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0,1	0,1
d_ULS	16,832	16,832
d_G	5,960	5,960
Chi-Square	6848	6848
NFI	0,814	0,814

From the table above the SRMR value is 0.1 so it can be concluded that this research model is acceptable. If it is concluded that the NFI ranges from 0.8 to 0.9, then this research model is classified as Marginal Fit.

E. Hypothesis Testing

Fig 4 Hypothesis Testing

Based on fig 4 above, the magnitude of the T statistic for the Type of Payment variable is 0.589 (smaller than 1.96) and the P values are 0.556 (greater than 0.05), meaning that the Type of Payment has no significant effect on Customer Satisfaction. This has meaning if the Type of Payment has nothing to do with Customer Satisfaction.

The results of this study are not relevant to research. In research conducted by Rosida, et al (2020) concluded that the online payment system has a positive effect on customer satisfaction in PDAM Makassar city.

It can be said that this type of payment cannot immediately increase or encourage customer satisfaction with the "KRISNA" refill gallon water product. This may be due to the types of payments made by customers that can be made in various ways and almost all depots use the same payment system as "KRISNA" refill gallons of water.

Based on fig 4 above, the magnitude of the T statistic for the Sales Promotion variable is 4.118 (greater than 1.96) and the P values are 0.000 (greater than 0.05), meaning that Sales Promotion has a significant effect on customer satisfaction. It can be said that the better Sales Promotion is carried out in marketing "KRISNA" refill gallon water, the customer satisfaction will increase.

The results of this study are in line with Putra and Rahmawati (2022) in their research which concluded that promotions partially affect customer satisfaction with bottled water for the LeMinerale brand, Tabanan Regency, Bali in the new normal era. In the research conducted by Putri, et. Al (2022) stated that the promotion variable provided by CV. Tirta Mitra Sejati has proven to have a significant effect on purchasing decisions. The number of samples studied in this study was 96 people. This research is also in line with Sukoco's research (2018) in which the promotion strategy has a significant effect on customer satisfaction at PT Tujuh Impian Bersama.

Based on fig 4, the magnitude of the T statistic for the variable Service Quality is 4.376 (greater than 1.96) and the P values are 0.000 (smaller than 0.05), meaning that Service Quality has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction. This means that the higher the value of service quality on customer satisfaction, the stronger the customer's motivation to feel satisfied. If the quality of service provided by "KRISNA" refill water meets customer expectations, it will indirectly encourage customers to become more loyal to the "KRISNA" refill water depot and create customer satisfaction.

The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Tijang et al., which concluded that there is a significant influence between Service Quality and consumer satisfaction in drinking water in Indonesia. According to Aprilia's research (2021), it states that the service quality variable has a significant effect on the customer satisfaction variable which was carried out some time ago.

Based on fig 4 above, the magnitude of the T statistic for the price variable is 0.923 (smaller than 1.96) and the P values are 0.356 (greater than 0.05), meaning that price has no positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction. This is because many refill gallon water depots sell the same price as the "KRISNA" refill gallon water depot.

The results of this study are not relevant to the research conducted by Renata (2020) who concluded that price has a significant effect on repeat purchases with customer satisfaction as an intervening variable. While on Aprilia's research (2021) states that price has a significant effect on customer satisfaction variables. This is also in line with research results (Agustina, et al, 2019) showing that there is a strong and positive relationship between product quality and price on customer satisfaction.

Based fig 4 above, the magnitude of the T statistic for the location variable is 0.139 (smaller than 1.96) and the P values are 0.889 (greater than 0.05), meaning that location has no positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction.

The results of this study are not relevant to Herlina (2019) that location variables have a positive and significant influence on customer satisfaction at AMIU Bilqis RO. This can be interpreted that the better the location of the company, the higher customer satisfaction will form and vice versa. However, this research is in line with research conducted by Fatimah (2015) which states that location/place/distribution does not have a partial effect on customer satisfaction. This research is also in line with Sulistiyanto (2020) stating that the location variable has no significant effect on customer purchasing decisions at the Moya Syariah Surakarta depot. This is also in line with research conducted by Firdiyansyah (2017) which states that location partially has a positive effect on customer satisfaction.

Based on fig 4 above, the magnitude of the T statistic for the variable Customer Satisfaction is 2.245 (greater than 1.96) and the P values are 0.025 (less than 0.05), meaning that Customer Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on repeat purchases.

The results of this study are in line with Kusuma and Suryani (2017) stating that customer satisfaction has a positive influence on repeat purchases. He also mentioned that customer satisfaction can mediate positively and significantly to repurchase intention. This is also in line with Sugiharto's research (2018) by taking the total population in his research as all customers of Cleo's bottled drinking water, totaling 57,806 people, and it can be concluded that customer satisfaction has a significant effect on repeat purchases of Cleo Di Bottled Water (AMDK). Kelurahan Gunung Anyar Surabaya so that it can be said that with high customer satisfaction it can increase repeat purchases. This research is in line with Saidani (2019) which states that customer satisfaction also has an influence on repurchasing decisions for refilled water products.

Based on fig 4 above, the magnitude of the T statistic for the variable Customer Satisfaction is 0.756 (smaller than 1.96) and the P values are 0.452 (greater than 0.05), meaning that the type of payment has no positive and significant effect on repeat purchases.

This research is in line with Yuliantika (2018) who concluded that Cash on Delivery payments for online shopping have a positive and significant effect on Shopee

customer repurchases. This is in line with research conducted by Nuryadin (2021) where Cash Back payments have a significant effect on Consumer Repurchase Decisions to Make Transactions Through E' commerce Tokopedia During the Covid-19 Pandemic Lockdown Period in the City of Banjarmasin. However, this study states that the type of payment has no positive and significant effect on repurchasing which is in line with research conducted by Watini (2017) which states that the payment system has no significant effect on repurchasing refill water in Cipayung Village, Bogor.

Based on fig 4 above, the magnitude of the T statistic for the variable Customer Satisfaction is 2.594 (greater than 1.96) and the P values are 0.010 (less than 0.05), meaning that Sales Promotion has a positive and significant effect on repeat purchases.

This research is relevant to research conducted by Yuzwar (2020) which says that promotions have a significant influence on repurchasing interest at the Medina Syariah Plaza supermarket.

So, it can be concluded that the effect of sales promotion on the satisfaction of repurchasing "KRISNA" gallon refills in this study concluded that sales promotion is a necessity for customers who are aware of the importance of product promotion, where this will affect repeat purchases. If the promotion is carried out continuously, the possibility of repurchasing will increase. In Rosaliana's research (2018) Through increasing Sales Promotion and Service Quality can increase repeat purchases.

Based on fig 4 above, the magnitude of the T statistic for the Quality-of-Service variable is 3.488 (greater than 1.96) and the P values are 0.001 (smaller than 0.05), meaning that Service Quality has a positive and significant effect on repeat purchases.

This is in line with research conducted by According to Langi (2022) which states that service quality and location have a positive and significant influence on re-purchasing of blue brand refill drinking water in Tebet Barat with 96 respondents who subscribe to blue water products. In research conducted by Ardiansyah (2015) who concluded that service quality has an indirect effect on repeat purchases. This is also in line with the research of Marbun et.al (2022) which concluded that Service Quality affects Repeat Purchases. Furthermore, in Sari and Hariyana's research (2019) concluded that service quality has a positive and significant effect on repurchase intention.

Based on fig 4 above, the magnitude of the T statistic for the price variable is 3.907 (greater than 1.96) and the P values are 0.000 (smaller than 0.05), meaning that price has a positive and significant effect on repeat purchases.

This research is not in line with Kusdyah (2016) which states that price perception has no effect on repurchasing intentions. This is also irrelevant to research conducted by Ismaya (2021) which states that price does not partially affect the repurchase of Waroeng Market Flamboyan. However,

research This is in line with research conducted by Melisa (2018) which states that price has a significant effect on repurchase decisions by distributing questionnaires to 100 respondents.

Based on fig 4 above, the magnitude of the T statistic for the location variable is 2.722 (greater than 1.96) and the P values are 0.007 (smaller than 0.05), meaning that location has a positive and significant effect on repeat purchase.

The research above is relevant to research conducted by Ismayana (2021) which states that location has a partial effect

on repurchasing Waroeng Market among 100 respondents. This is also in line with research by Lubis (2015) which states that a location close to the customer's home will make it easier for the customer to buy refill water because it is easy to reach. So that can conclude that location has a significant effect on repurchasing decisions on refill water products in Tanjung Harapan Village. Based on the results of Yunus' research (2016) it is known that location has a positive and significant effect on consumer repurchasing of the Harapan J2 coffee shop in Palu City.

Table 10 Mean, STDEV, T-Values, P-Values

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values
Price Percept -> Consumer Satisfaction -> Repurchase	0,012	0,010	0,014	0,856	0,392
Payment-> Consumer Satisfaction -> Repurchase	0,008	0,008	0,015	0,535	0,593
Service Quality -> Consumer Satisfaction -> Repurchase	0,053	0,054	0,030	1,794	0,073
Location-> Consumer Satisfaction -> Repurchase	0,002	0,003	0,014	0,131	0,896
Sales Promotion -> Consumer Satisfaction -> Repurchase	0,045	0,043	0,021	2,105	0,036

Source: SmartPLS V.3.0 output

Based on the results of the study it was found that customer satisfaction intervened in the relationship between sales promotion and repurchase with P values below 0.05, namely 0.036, but no intervening effect was found on customer satisfaction in the type of payment variable with repurchase with P values above 0.05, namely 0.593, quality services with repurchase with P values above 0.05, namely 0.073, prices with repurchase with P Values above 0.05, namely 0.0392 and locations with repurchase with P values above 0.05, namely 0.896. So, it can be concluded that customer satisfaction can be an intervening relationship between sales promotion and repurchasing, while the relationship between the type of payment, service quality, price and location with repurchasing work cannot be used as an intervening. In this study, the variable Customer Satisfaction cannot be used as a mediation between Price and Location for Repurchasing which is relevant to research conducted by Akbar and Nurcholis (2020) which states that Customer Satisfaction cannot be used as a mediation between price and location for repurchasing decisions.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

A. Conclusion

- The type of payment has no significant effect on customer satisfaction with "KRISNA" refill gallons of water.
- Sales Promotion has a significant effect on customer satisfaction for the "KRISNA" refill gallon water product
- Quality of service has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction for the "KRISNA" refill gallon water product.

- Perception Perception of price does not have a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction of "KRISNA" refill gallon water
- Location has no significant effect on customer satisfaction of "KRISNA" refill gallon water
- Customer satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on repurchasing KRISNA refill gallons of water
- The type of payment has no positive and significant effect on the repurchase of KRISNA refill gallons of water
- Sales Promotion has a positive and significant effect on the Repurchase of KRISNA refill gallon water
- Quality of Service has a positive and significant effect on the Repurchase of KRISNA refill gallons of water
- Price perception has a positive and significant effect on the purchase of refill gallons of KRISNA water
- Location has a positive and significant effect on the Repurchase of KRISNA refill gallon water
- Customer satisfaction cannot be used as mediation in the relationship between the type of payment, service quality, price, and location for the Repurchase of "KRISNA" refill gallon water
- Customer satisfaction can be used as mediation in the relationship between Sales Promotion and Repurchasing of "KRISNA" refill water

B. Suggestions

➤ *Academic*

Based on the conclusions above, the researcher suggests for future researchers to re-test this research model at different locations and other refill gallon water objects. Considering that the F-square in the study is 0.686, it means that customer

satisfaction can only be influenced by sales promotion and service quality. While the variable type of payment, price and location have no effect on customer satisfaction. In addition, suggestions for future researchers are to process different research variables because customer quality cannot be used as mediation in the relationship between price, service quality, price, and location on repurchasing. Meanwhile, customer satisfaction can only mediate the relationship between sales promotion and repeat purchases.

➤ *Practical (KRISNA Refill Water Management)*

Based on the conclusions above, the researcher proposes several corrective actions to increase customer satisfaction and repurchase KRISNA refill gallon water as follows:

- The management of KRISNA refill water needs to increase sales promotion, because the sales promotion variable can increase customer satisfaction of KRISNA refill gallon water. Coupons are given in the form of purchases with coupons 10 times get 1 gallon free.
- KRISNA's refill water management can provide special prices because customers want special prices when purchasing refill water. With this special price, customers have reasons to buy again and again. The special price given is for stalls or shops that deliberately buy refill gallons of water for resale.
- The management of KRISNA's refilled water needs to improve the quality of service, because of the service quality variable that can make KRISNA's refilled gallons of water customers feel satisfied and able to buy again and again. By serving customers on the same day as the day of the order. In addition, management must improve the timeliness of delivery of refill water so that customers are satisfied. By delivering water and offering to pour gallons of water into the Dispenser, customers, who are mostly housewives, will be motivated to buy "KRISNA" refill gallons of water.
- Management of KRISNA's refill water to improve parking safety, so that customers feel safe and comfortable when buying refilled gallons of water, they come directly to the location of the refill water depot. With a competitor for the "Blue" brand which is only one and a half kilometers away, it is necessary to be alert to improve a safer and more comfortable location when customers buy directly at the "KRISNA" refill water location

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